

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

BIOACCUMULATION OF TOXIC ELEMENTS IN THE PLANT SYSTEM

Karimov Kh.,

Doctor of agricultural sciences, senior researcher

Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named after Academician M. Mirzayev

Nurmetov N.

doctoral student

Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemical Research

ABSTRACT

In laboratory experiments, the bioaccumulation of Cu, Zn, Pb, Ni, Cd, Cr, Co toxicants in the stem, root and grain of rice in the condition of soil composition 3 and 5 times higher than MPCs, and in the case of complex pollution of the elements, was highlighted. With a large amount of bioaccumulation of toxicants in the root system of the plant, the accumulation of heavy metal ions in the stem and grain was determined to be less than the MPC for the plant.

Keywords: soil, rice plant, heavy metals, bioaccumulation, maximum permissible concentration (MPC).

Introduction. In order to increase the productivity of irrigated areas, to improve land reclamation and water supply, large-scale irrigation and land reclamation measures are being implemented within the framework of state programs. However, as a result of global climate change, periodic water shortages and the failure of the main part of internal irrigation networks in recent years have led to the deterioration of irrigated cropland land reclamation and its disuse for years.

Agricultural land areas are affected by heavy metal contamination of agricultural products, first of all, they cause negative effects as a result of the movement of existing toxicants in the trophic chain system "atmosphere → soil → plant → product → animal ↔ human". Toxic heavy metals accumulate in the human body as a result of entering the human body with plant products.

Review of literature. Heavy metal toxicity has proven to be a major threat and there are several human health risks associated with it. The toxic effects of these metals, although they have no biological role, are present in one form or another and MPCain harmful to the human body and its proper functioning. A few metals, such as aluminum, can be MPCoved through elimination, while some metals accumulate in the body and in the food chain, causing chronic disease [16]. Heavy metals enter the human body through the gastrointestinal tract, through the skin or by inhalation [32]. The development of industrial activity in the last century has increased the level of heavy metal exposure to people. Mercury, lead, chromium, cadmium, and zinc were the most common heavy metals causing human poisoning [5].

The analysis of heavy metals in the soil was carried out on the basis of the "Methodological manual for

the determination of heavy metals in agricultural areas by soil and plant products types", 5 grams of soil passed through 0.25 mm sieves were dissolved in 1 normal HNO₃ acid, prepared aqueous solution AVIO- Tested on 200 hardware [37; - 61 p.].

After determining the quantitative indicators of heavy metals detected in the soil, in 2021-2022 in 3 replicates based on 19 options, the Microvegetation "Miniature" Neibauer experiment was carried out on artificially polluted soils in the Alanga and Lazer varieties of rice based on the modified analyzes of Golodkovskii.

4 kg of soil was mainly contaminated in containers with a height of 35 cm and a diameter of 25 cm. During the decontamination process, 4 kg of soil was mixed with heavy metal salts weighed on an analytical balance. First of all, while thoroughly mixing boron salts with 4 kg of soil, first 50 grams of soil, then 100 grams of soil were taken and mixed. In this case, the soil was added little by little and mixed well.

The copper element in the soil selected for our laboratory research was found to be 8.78 mg/kg on average, 2.93 times more than MPC (MPC -3 mg/kg). Cadmium element ions were found to be 0.43 mg/kg, less than MPC (MPC – 0.5 mg/kg).

The mobile form of the chromium element is 3.29 mg/kg, which is less than MPC (MPC - 6 mg/kg) as the composition of elements in parent rock. MPC of cobalt soil is 5 mg/kg, and it was found to be 3.08 mg/kg in our selected soils. The MPC of nickel in soil was determined to be 4 mg/kg, and it was found to be 2.01 times higher in soil. The MPC of zinc element ions in the soil was determined to be 23 mg/kg, which was found to be 0.06 times higher than the MPC (Table 3).

Table 3

Amount of heavy metals in mobile form in typical irrigated gray soils, mg/kg

Cu	Cd	Cr	Co	Pb	Ni	Zn
8.78	0.43	3.29	3.08	12.07	5.62	24.58

In order to determine the amount of elements in the soil, the selected soils were artificially contaminated with toxicants 3 and 5 times more than the MPC for soil (Table 4).

Table 4

Amount of salt obtained for artificial pollution of irrigated typical gray soils with toxic elements, mg/4kg

No	Chemical salts	5 in the case of MPC	3 in the case of MPC
1	CoSO ₄	2,63	19.70
2	CuSO ₄	1.50	11.30
3	NiSO ₄ *7H ₂ O	3.80	28.70
4	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	1.90	14.40
5	ZnSO ₄ *7H ₂ O	20,20	151.70
6	CdCl ₂	0.20	1.20
7	K ₂ CrO ₄	4.50	33.60

For laboratory experiments, it was taken from the plow layer of the soil of the institute's garden. The soil is well supplied with mobile forms of nutrients according to supply analyses.

It is known that the average content of humus is 2.04-1.93%, 26.55-47.40 mg/kg with mobile phosphorus, 387-398 mg/kg with potassium, and 7.85% of carbonate (Table 5).

Table 5

Agrochemical properties of irrigated typical gray soils

Section no	Depth, cm	Hummus, %	Active mg/kg		CO ₂
			P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
Garden	0-30	2.04±0.042	26.55±0.050	387±10.61	7.85±0.057
	0-30				

In experiments carried out at the University of Calcutta, India, chromium content in rice straw accumulated higher than in rice grain, and Cr content in rice grain had the highest correlation with water-soluble and exchangeable Cr ($r=0.99^{**}$) [7]. Chromium (Cr) is beneficial to some plants and animals in small amounts, but in high concentrations it can be a dangerous environmental pollutant [27].

Effects on two rice cultivars were investigated by Basit et al., and found to have negative effects on plant biomass and photosynthetic rate [6]. It reduced the accumulation of large amounts of carbon dioxide in the soil and improved grain quality under Cr toxicity. It has been found that growing rice in a CO₂-enriched environment can reduce the risk of chromium toxicity and support its quality [1]. The plant root absorbs and accumulates Cr from the soil, causing its presence in the aerial parts of the plant through a passive pathway, so it can affect human health through the food chain [11]. Absorption of Cr has been found to reduce the ability of plant roots to absorb essential nutrients [31].

Absorption of micro- and macro-element ions from the soil, mainly through the root system, is carried out by the process of bioaccumulation, distributed to all parts of the plant.

Chromium element ion was found to be less accumulated in the roots of the flame and laser variety, that is, in the flame variety. In the 2021 laboratory experiments, the control variant of the flame variety accumulated 0.47 mg/kg, and the laser variety accumulated 3.52 mg/kg, i.e. more than 3.05 mg. In 2022, the accumulation of 3.52 mg/kg was observed in the roots of the

flame cultivar, while it bioaccumulated 1.66 mg less in the laser cultivar.

When the soil content was artificially contaminated with 3 and 5 times the permissible limit of toxic elements (MPC), 0.77 mg/kg was accumulated in the roots of the flame variety and 6.01 mg/kg in the laser variety. 2022 was recorded to be 0.68 mg/kg and 4.98 mg/kg respectively during the season. Chromium bioaccumulation of 1.45 mg/kg in the roots of the flame variety and 10.99 mg/kg in the laser variety was determined in the analysis by seasons of the varieties contaminated with 3 times more than the MPC, and 9.54 mg per kilogram of root in the laser variety compared to the flame variety. /kg has been found to accumulate more.

In variants with 5 times more contamination than MPC, the roots of the flame variety absorbed a total of 1.47 mg/kg of elemental ion in two seasons, while the laser variety paid a total of 11.81 mg/kg.

In the experimental options, when the soil composition was polluted 3 times more than the standard with the complex effects of elements (Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn) compared to the norm, the total amount of 1.64 mg/kg in the roots of the flame cultivar was 1.64 mg/kg during two seasons and 5 times in the complex polluted options. 2.94 mg/kg was found to accumulate. It was determined that 5.99 mg/kg in the first season and 3.60 mg/kg in the second season were accumulated in the roots of laser variety in the variant with 3 times more MPC. It was found that 5.67 mg/kg in the first season and 4.79 mg/kg in the second season bioaccumulated from the variant soils with 5 times MPC (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Bioaccumulation of chromium element ions in rice roots, mg/kg

In conclusion, the abundance or deficiency of elements in the soil requires the study of the bioaccumulation of elemental ions in the root system and parts of the varieties, that is, the difference in the accumulation in the root system of annual and perennial plant varieties belonging to the conifers, requires their selective planting in polluted areas.

In the research conducted by Bhattacharyya et al., it was reported that the amount of chromium accumulated in the rice stalk is more than that [7]. Soil contamination with chromium (Cr) reduces rice yield and quality. Future climate CO₂ (eCO₂) is known to affect crop growth and yield, as well as quality parameters related to human health. However, it has been mentioned that the detailed physiological and biochemical responses induced by Cr in rice grains produced under eCO₂ have not been thoroughly investigated [2].

It was found that the mobile forms of heavy metals in the stem part of rice cultivars took up element ions in large quantities from MPC-contaminated soils 3 and 5 times higher than the control variant.

In the samples taken from the control variants during two seasons, the highest bioaccumulation of the

flame cultivar was detected in the stem part compared to all the other contaminated variants, with an accumulation of 0.61 mg/kg. Chromium accumulation in the stems of plants contaminated with elements 3 and 5 times and complex with elements (3 and 5 times) was found to be in the following order: control soil - (0.61 mg/kg) → Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil (0.56 mg/kg) → Cr (3 MPC) + soil (0.51 mg/kg) → Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil (0.50 mg/kg) → Cr (3 MPC) + soil (0.49 mg/kg).

High accumulation of chromium in the root system of the Lazer cultivar has been found to result in high bioaccumulation of toxicants in the stem itself. In 2021, 1.0 mg/kg was accumulated in variants contaminated with 3 times the MPC of the element, but it was 0.79 mg/kg in 2022, a decrease of 0.22 milligrams compared to 2021. A total of 1.79 mg/kg was accumulated. This situation was also observed in the 5-fold MPC contaminated version of the element, with a total accumulation of 1.76 mg/kg (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Chromium ion bioaccumulation in stems, mg/kg

Cr complexed with elements was accumulated in relatively high amounts in the stems of the flame variety of the experimental variants contaminated with 3-5 times of the MPCs. 0.91 mg/kg in 2021 and 0.69 mg/kg in 2022 from MPC1a 3 times contaminated variant, 1.02 mg/kg in 2022 and 0.66 mg/kg in 2022 from MPC1a 5 times complex variants and bioaccumulation of 1.68 mg/kg was determined (Fig. 4).

In conclusion, a high accumulation of chromium element was observed in the stem part of the laser compared to the flame variety, regardless of the state of pollution, in all options, the average of 0.27 mg/kg in the stem part of the flame variety in 2021-2022, in the stem part of the laser in 2021, on average 0, 88 mg/kg, and in 2022 it was observed to accumulate around 0.65 mg/kg.

If the MPC is 0.5 mg/kg for chromium element in the grain, it is 3 and 5 times more than the MPC and some accumulation in the grain part, as in the stem and roots, was detected in complex contamination.

In the work carried out by the researchers, it was determined that the bioaccumulation of chromium in the grains of 2 types of rice differs from each other. A high amount of Cr6+ ions was accumulated in Sakha 106 grain [2].

In the grains obtained from the Lazer and Alanga varieties of our research, Cr was accumulated in 2021 at 0.17 and 0.02 mg/kg, respectively, in the control options. In 2022, it was determined that 0.79 and 0.46 mg/kg were collected from the soil of the control option.

Chromium was observed to be 0.14 mg/kg in 2021 and 1.66 mg/kg in plant bioaccumulation due to the

abundance of the toxicant in the soil and complete distribution of ions in the soil layer in 2021, in accordance with control options.

In the first year when the variant soils were contaminated 3 and 5 times, in the control variant - 0.34, in the variant with Cr (3 MPC) - 0.29, in the variant with Cr (5 MPC) - 0.23, Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+ in the version with Co+Zn (3 MPC) - 0.21, in the version with Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) - 0.31 mg/kg, it was determined that less amount of MPC was accumulated. In the laser variety, it was collected 0.03→0.09→0.15→0.12→0.17 times less, respectively.

As shown in the table, a higher bioaccumulation of the element was observed in grains harvested from rice varieties planted in the second year than in the first year. The control variant Alanga was accumulated 1.57 times higher than MPC, 3.31 and 2.94 times higher in 3-fold and 5-fold contamination, 2.43 times higher in the complex 3-fold contaminated variant, and 2.45 times higher in the complex 3-fold contaminated variant. Compared to the grain of the Alanga variety, it is less than MPC in the grain of the control variant, i.e. 0.91 times less, the toxicant is accumulated by 1.53 times in the 3-fold contaminated variant, and it is accumulated 1.78 times less compared to the amount of ions in the Alanga variety grain.

In complex fermentation, Alanga grain contains the highest 1.21-1.23 mg/kg, 3- and 5-fold complex (Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn) contamination of toxic elements. 74 and 5.83 times higher, that is, bioaccumulation was observed in the amount of 2.87-2.92 mg/kg (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Bioaccumulation of chromium ion in grain, mg/kg

In conclusion, contamination newly introduced into the soil or observed in the first year does not directly bioaccumulate in the planted plant. In the second year, the element entered with the soil fractions moves through plant roots in different parts and accumulates in more or less quantity.

Table 6

Chromium ion bioaccumulation analysis in plant organs of Alanga variety of rice, mean of 3 replicates

Options	Root		Stem		Grain	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	0.47±0.12	0.37±0.88	0.37±0.04	0.51±0.03	0.17±0.04	0.79±0.04
Cr (3 MPC) + soil	0.77±0.08	6.01±2.95	0.24±0.05	1.00±0.03	0.14±0.03	1.66±0.17
Cr (5 MPC) + soil	0.75±0.17	7.19±0.17	0.21±0.03	0.98±0.12	0.12±0.04	1.47±0.02
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+ Zn (3 MPC) + soil	0.90±0.20	5.99±3.08	0.27±0.02	0.91±0.02	0.11±0.03	1.21±0.02
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+ Zn (5 MPC) + soil	2.19±1.47	5.67±1.49	0.24±0.01	1.02±0.02	0.16±0.03	1.23±0.07

Table 7

Chromium ion bioaccumulation assays in plant organs of Lazer cultivar of rice, mean of 3 replicates

Options	Root		Stem		Grain	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	0.47±0.49	1.86±0.44	0.24±0.05	0.44±0.02	0.02±0.00	0.46±0.10
Cr (3 MPC) + soil	0.68±0.08	4.98±0.59	0.27±0.08	0.79±0.05	0.05±0.01	0.77±0.16
Cr (5 MPC) + soil	0.72±0.06	4.62±1.94	0.28±0.08	0.78±0.14	0.08±0.01	0.47±0.02
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	0.74±0.16	3.60±0.90	0.23±0.06	0.69±0.07	0.06±0.01	2.87±1.01
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	0.75±0.06	4.79±0.85	0.32±0.06	0.66±0.03	0.09±0.06	2.92±0.0.02

Copper is an essential element for plant growth and development, but it is toxic to plants in high concentrations.

In studies by Hu, Jiaquan et al. It was determined that Cu has a toxic effect on the rice crop, that is, its productivity decreases. In agar, it was found to be reduced by about 10% at 100 mg/kg of copper, at 300-500 mg/kg by 50%, and at 1000 mg/kg by about 90%. Accumulation of 60% in the polished rice grain, 24% in the kernel, and 12% in the straw part is reported [33].

In a study by Yu-Ping Yan et al. on 38 varieties of rice, it was found to be higher in brown rice than in the control, and did not exceed 10 mg/kg in the MPCaining varieties.[34].

In the laboratory experiment, bioaccumulation of the copper element was also observed in rice organs

from MPCs 3 and 5 and complex 3 and 5 times contaminated soils, except for the control variant. In the control variant soil, copper was accumulated at 2.04 mg/kg in the roots of Laser variety of rice due to higher MPC. In 2021, when the soil was contaminated with one type of copper element, the root system had a high bioaccumulation of 14.86 mg/kg (1.49 times from MPC) and 15.16 mg/kg (1.51 times from MPC) when it was 5 MPC. It was found that 10 mg/kg in MPC rice was accumulated in complex contamination, 3.17 and 4.86 mg/kg in the root system, and it was found to be 0.32 and 0.49 less than MPC. A low accumulation of copper was observed in the Alanga variety of rice, accumulating 0.95-1.73-1.74-2.24-1.94 mg/kg according to variants (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Bioaccumulation of copper ion in the root system, mg/kg

During the second vegetation period (2022), in the root system of rice, the amount of 5.41-1.69 mg/kg from the soil of the control variant of Alanga and Lazer varieties, 6.16-2.12 mg/kg from the 3 times polluted variants, 5 times polluted variant 7.72 mg/kg in the roots of the Alanga variety and 4.50 mg/kg in the roots of the Lazer variety were collected from the soils.

7.65-8.84 and 4.41-4.51 mg/kg of elements were accumulated in the roots of Alanga and Lazer cultivars from variant soils 3 and 5 times contaminated with MPCs (Fig. 6).

In conclusion, low bioaccumulation of copper was found in the roots of both cultivars, and despite the presence of soil contamination in the root system, as in the conducted studies, it was found that elemental ions are poorly absorbed. It was found that the maximum amount of the index bioaccumulated 1.51 times more than MPCs in case of 5-fold exposure with copper element and with complex elements.

The highest accumulation of the element in the stems of the variety "Alanga" was observed in the first year, 1.25 mg/kg in the control variant, 2.40 and 1.47 mg/kg in the 3- and 5-fold polluted soils (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Bioaccumulation of copper ion in the stem part of varieties, mg/kg

The highest rate was determined in 3-fold complex pollution, and the accumulation of the element in the amount of 4.01 mg/kg, in the case of 5-fold complex pollution was determined to be 2.26 mg/kg. In 2022, it was determined that the plant stem absorbed the element from 3 and 5 times polluted soil around 1.17-1.13 mg/kg (Fig. 7).

1.78 mg/kg was accumulated in the stem part of the Lazer variety in the control option in 2021, 1.39-2.16-2.14-1.80 mg/kg in the other options, and in 2022 these indicators were significantly less, respectively 0,18→0.53→0.15→0.23→0.88 mg/kg (Figure 7). Bioaccumulation was observed in the stem part of the selected varieties for two years, less than the amount allowed for the plant.

In the studies conducted by scientists, it was mentioned that the accumulation of copper ions in large amounts in rice grains depends on the varieties [33-34]. The transfer factor of the detected heavy metals from soil to rice was determined in the following order: Zn > Cu > Cr > Co > Cd > Pb > Fe > As > Ni [13]. Cadmium (Cd), lead (As) and lead (Pb) were found to be the most prevalent metals in rice cultivation. Mining and irrigation activities are the main sources, but the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides also contributes to heavy metal contamination of soil around the world. In addition to their negative impact on the soil ecosystem by reducing soil fertility and grain yield, heavy metal contamination poses a threat to human health [35].

A study conducted by Singh et al. [28] in Ramgarh Lake, India showed that, apart from Cd and As, Zn, Cr, Cu and Pb elemental ions were found to be relatively more abundant in different parts of rice plants from rice plant soil and this was related to their adsorptive status [20].

In 2021, it was found that copper ions in the grain obtained from the Alanga and Lazer varieties were collected at 1.45-1.84 mg/kg in the control options. The process of bioaccumulation continued around 1.45-2.06 mg/kg from 3 times polluted soil, 1.63-1.67 mg/kg from 5 times polluted soil.

During the 2022 growing season, 0.32→0.54→1.11→0.40 mg/kg was accumulated in the grain part of Alanga obtained from soil contaminated with 3 and 5 times of control, 3 times and 5 times of complex MPC. It was found that only the complex was 1.18 times more than MPC in grain content from 5 times contaminated soils.

In the grain content of the Lazer variety, the situation similar to that of the Alanga variety was repeated, and it was found that it collected 3 and 5 times less complex with 7 types of elements than MPC from the contaminated soil, and bioaccumulation was observed in the following order: 0.31→0.36→0.39→1.20→1.39 mg/kg (Figure 8). This situation exactly replicated the situation among 38 cultivars conducted by Yu-Ping Yan et al. Because bioaccumulation of copper was not observed in the grain part [34].

Figure 8. Bioaccumulation of copper in grain, mg/kg

Table 8

Analyses of copper ion bioaccumulation in plant organs of rice cultivar Alanga, mean of 3 replicates

Options	Root		Stem		Grain	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	0.95±0.14	5.41±1.22	1.25±0.16	0.03±0.01	1.45±0.43	0.32±0.28
Cu (3 MPC) + soil	1.73±0.68	6.10±1.62	2.40±1.67	0.11±0.03	1.45±0.43	0.54±0.21
Cu (5 MPC) + soil	1.74±0.27	7.72±0.33	1.47±0.15	0.58±0.02	1.63±0.24	1.11±0.30
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	2.34±1.02	7.72±3.83	4.01±1.91	1.17±0.05	2.13±0.33	0.40±0.38
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	1.94±1.16	8.84±4.38	2.26±0.78	1.13±0.18	2.28±0.56	11.82±0.14

Table 9

Analysis of copper ion bioaccumulation in plant organs of rice variety Lazer, mean of 3 replicates

Options	Root		Stem		Grain	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	2.04±1.80	1.69±0.49	1.78±0.08	0.18±0.09	1.83±1.11	0.31±0.03
Cu (3 MPC) + soil	14.86±2.01	2.12±0.56	1.39±0.26	0.53±0.06	2.05±0.39	0.36±0.02
Cu (5 MPC) + soil	15.16±1.49	4.50±0.98	2.16±0.65	0.15±0.09	1.67±0.09	0.39±0.09
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	3.17±0.12	4.41±0.75	2.14±0.67	0.23±0.07	1.92±0.44	1.20±0.01
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	4.86±3.80	4.51±0.97	1.80±0.55	0.88±0.32	2.68±0.82	1.39±0.08

Zn is a transition metal that usually exists in nature in its divalent state. It is an essential mineral because it is necessary for the production of hundreds of enzymes throughout the body. The recommended daily intake of zinc varies by patient population, and the normal serum zinc concentration is 109-130 micrograms/dL. It acts as a cofactor in enzymatic reactions involved in DNA expression, membrane stabilization, vitamin A metabolism, and the taste and smell systems [29]. It has many functions, that is, the contribution of zinc in the growth and development of the fetus. In addition, a characteristic feature of the function of zinc in the body is its

inverse relationship with copper levels, and it is often part of pharmaceutical preparations used in the treatment of Wilson's disease [8]. Chronic zinc toxicity manifests primarily as copper deficiency [4].

Zinc is an important factor in the body and is necessary for normal functioning. As zinc levels increase, toxicity may also increase. There are three types of exposure that can cause toxicity: inhalation, oral, and dermal [3].

An increase in soil pH with biochar application helped to reduce the available Zn concentration in rice soil [15].

In the research within the framework of the ongoing practical project, it is intended to identify soil pollution and selectively plant plants that absorb the amount of toxicants, so it is necessary to plant only plants in a toxic environment and determine which type of plant is tolerant to pollution.

The MPC for the mobile form of zinc in the soil is set at 50 mg/kg. 4.11 mg/kg of zinc ions were accumulated in the root system of the control variant. In 2022,

a decrease of 2.39 mg/kg was observed. It was found that the variant contaminated with Zn element 3 and 5 times increased to 3.40-4.70 mg/kg, and from complex contaminated soils to 9.65-7.94 mg/kg. In the root system of the Laser cultivar, accumulation was found from 14.85 mg/kg in the control variant, to 6.58 mg/kg in the second year (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Bioaccumulation of zinc ions in the root system

The highest bioaccumulation in the root part of the Laser variety was determined in the second year in the variant contaminated with 5 times more chemical elements than MPCs, and accumulated in the amount of 18.66 mg/kg. The bioaccumulation of 45.14 mg/kg was observed in the roots of the flame variety of zinc, which was lower than MPC in both varieties (Figure 9).

Low bioaccumulation of Zn in roots of both cultivars may lead to high accumulation in grain and other

plant parts. Because this condition is observed in all plants.

Bioaccumulation of zinc in the stem part was found to be 8.54 and 12.6 mg/kg and 15.2 and 9.52 mg/kg in the first and second vegetation period of the Alanga variety from the soil of the control variant (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Bioaccumulation of zinc ions in the stem part of varieties, mg/kg

For the soil, in the 3 times more polluted version with MPC, in the first and second growing season, the amount was slightly higher in the stems of the Alanga variety compared to the control, i.e. 14.08 and 19.38 mg/kg, and in the stems of the Lazer variety, 14.25 and 23.38 mg/kg. bioaccumulation in the amount of kg was observed. 31.52 mg/kg was accumulated in the stems of plants from MPC 5 and complex 3 and 5 times polluted variant soils in Lazer variety. The highest amount of Zn accumulation was observed in the stems of Alanga cultivar, which was 1.28 times higher than MPC in the first growing season, and decreased by 27.19 mg/kg in the second year (Figure 10).

The introduction of microelements in rice feeding is a mandatory element of high technology, writes A.H. Sheudgen. It is associated with insufficient mobile forms of micronutrient compounds to the rice-planted soils, of which boron, cobalt, molybdenum - 2 kg/ha, copper - 3 kg/ha, zinc and manganese - 4 kg/ha, when applying 2.9-6.3 ts of productivity increases to /. It has been mentioned that foliar feeding with 0.1% aqueous solutions of these elements increases the yield of rice by 3.6-5.4 t/ha [38]. But the increase of these microelements in MPCs leads to a lot of bioaccumulation in different parts of rice and has a toxic effect on the consumer.

Zinc content in spring wheat plants varied from 5.8 to 7.6 mg/kg in straw and 30.8 to 34.3 mg/kg in grain, depending on feeding background. The coefficient of biological absorption is 13.1-12.8; the coefficient of biological accumulation is 14.9-15.9. It shows that zinc participates most intensively in the biochemical cycle of agrocenosis in spring wheat cultivation, and

its deficiency becomes a limiting factor for productivity [36].

In the experiments carried out with the addition of different types of MPCs, the accumulation of zinc element in the grain part of rice in the control variant was 21.02 mg/kg in the first vegetation period in the Alanga variety, 22.45 mg/kg in the Lazer variety, and during the second vegetation period, the indicators were generally similar in both varieties. , that is, 8.95 and 5.74 mg/kg were observed to bioaccumulate (Fig. 11).

High bioaccumulation was observed in the variant Zn (3 MPC) when the soil was contaminated with a mobile form of the element 3 and 5 times more than MPC. It was found that during the first and second vegetation period of the Alanga variety, a total of 53.75 mg/kg was accumulated in each kilogram of grain, and 60.70 mg/kg was accumulated in the Lazer variety. It was found that 15.72 m/kg in the grain of the Alanga variety and 17.14 mg/kg in the grain of the Lazer variety were found from the variant soils fed with the element 5 times more than MPC (Fig. 11).

With 3-fold complex pollution of soil composition with various elements, more than 2 mg/kg of MPC was observed in the grain part during the first vegetation. During two growing seasons, a total of 82.09 mg/kg of soil was 82.09 mg/kg, 69.96 mg/kg in grain of Lazer variety, and 58.62 mg/kg in grain of Alanga variety from soils of variant contaminated 5 times more than complex MPCs of elements. , and it was determined that 69.65 mg/kg was accumulated in Lazer grain. It was found that only the Lazer variety assimilated the same amount of Zn element in the grain part during two vegetation years (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Bioaccumulation of zinc ions in the grain part of varieties, mg/kg

In studies conducted by Hasan G. et al, Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Cr and Co, Ni and As were detected in soil and rice samples from three major industrial areas of Dhaka Division, Bangladesh. The mean concentrations of Fe, Cu and Zn are higher than those of Pb, Cr, Co, Ni and As, and the former have been shown to be the main pollutants in these industrial areas [14]. Umair Ashraf et al., all rice cultivars accumulated different concentrations of Pb in their organs. However, the general trend of Pb accumulation in different parts of the plant was noted as follows: root > stem > leaf > spike > grain [30].

Masoumeh Fouladi et al. reported that Pb accumulated in rice was 0.17 ± 0.08 , with an average soil content of 10.99 ± 4.30 mg/kg [19] was 1.83 times higher than MPC in the soil itself.

The MPC for the element of lead in the composition of cereal crops is set at 0.5 mg/kg, and the accumulation of Pb ions in the root system of plant varieties is found to be high. 0.35 mg/kg during the first season (2021), 4.02 mg/kg during the second season (2022), and 3.01 and 1.92 mg/kg were accumulated in the root system of the Alanga cultivar from the soil of the control variant. bioaccumulation was observed (Figure 12).

The artificial introduction of toxicants into the soil was observed to accumulate in the roots of plants in small amounts during the first season of the plant. Roots of both varieties accumulated 0.48-0.61 mg/kg

from 3-fold contaminated variants, 1.09-0.77 mg/kg from 5-fold contaminated variants. 1.01-0.78 mg/kg of elements were accumulated in 3-fold complex contaminated variants, and 1.64-0.89 mg/kg in 5-fold contaminated variants, and 1.54-3.28 times higher bioaccumulation than MPC was observed (Fig. 12).

During the second season, a sharp increase of these parameters was detected in the Alanga variety of rice, in the root system of the Alanga variety it was 8.15 mg/kg (16.3 times more than MPC), and in the Lazer variety it was 3.93 mg/kg (7.86 times more than MPC). It was 34.28 times more than MPC in 5 times contaminated variants and 11.24 times more in roots of Lazer variety.

This situation was also observed in the version of elements with 5 times more than complex MPCs, that is, 21.26 times more than MPC. It can be seen that the bioaccumulation of the elements differed between cultivars with 7.39 mg/kg accumulated in the root of the cultivar Lazer. During the second season, bioaccumulation of the element in the root system of both cultivars in the amount of 4.39-4.62 mg/kg was observed in the 3-fold complex polluted variants of the elements, and it can be seen that the accumulation of toxicants in the root system also depends on the MPCs of the toxic elements (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Bioaccumulation of lead ion in the root system, mg/kg

The condition observed in the roots of both varieties of rice can be seen with a low amount of bioaccumulation of elements in the stem. 0.22-0.38 mg/kg was accumulated in the stems of both cultivars in the control variants (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Bioaccumulation of lead in the stem part of rice varieties, mg/kg

It was found that the concentration of the element ion in the stem parts of the Lazer variety is higher than that of the Alanga variety, the element is accumulated 3 times and 5 times more in the complex contaminated variants up to 0.59-0.92 mg/kg, in MPCs up to 1.18-1.84 times. Bioaccumulation of elemental ions up to 0.21-0.52 mg/kg was observed in the stems of plants obtained from all other variants (Fig. 13).

Lead accumulated in the roots, stems, and leaves, bran, and husk of rice plants, from top to bottom, with undetectable amounts in white rice. The concentration of lead in rice grain did not exceed the food hygiene concentration limit. However, lead accumulated in

stems and leaves and bran can enter the food chain as animal feed or as mulch in vegetable production [22]. Rice plants accumulated lead in root (5.735 mg/kg), stem and leaves (0.0820 mg/kg) and grain (0.0169 mg/kg). The concentration of lead in rice grains did not exceed the EU standard for lead in legumes (0.2 mg/kg), indicating that seeds grown in lead-contaminated soil had acceptable levels [23].

In the course of the research, the lead element, like all elements, was examined using an Avio 200 Spectrometer in an aqueous absorption medium prepared using 1N HNO₃ acid.

The MPC for lead is set at 0.5 mg/kg in cereals. Due to the presence of MPC of Pb ion in the composition of the control soil, that is, the soil selected for the laboratory experiment, the content of the element in grain is 1.23 times higher than that of MPC, in the first season it was determined in the Alanga variety. In 2022, 0.48 mg/kg was detected in Alanga grain and it was found to be 0.963 times of MPC (Figure 14).

When the soils were artificially polluted for the first time (2021), the absorption of ions by plants is low, only from the variants of elements polluted 5 times more than MPC, lead in the grain part is 1.48 times more than MPC, i.e. 0.742 mg/kg. In the variant with toxicants 3 times higher than MPC, in the variant with elements complex toxicants 5 times higher than MPC, it is 1.54 times higher (0.768 mg/kg), it was determined that bioaccumulation of lead occurs in complex polluted areas of elements (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. Bioaccumulation of lead ions in cereals, mg/kg

In conclusion, lead contamination depends on the cultivar status of the plant, and the accumulation of elemental ions was observed in the grain of the Alanga variety compared to the grain of the Lazer variety.

The simultaneous effects of zero-valent iron (Fe^0) on the uptake, translocation, and bioaccumulation of cobalt (Co) and lead (Pb) in the grain of a rice cultivar (*Oryza sativa* L.) were investigated to mitigate Co and Pb toxicity in rice, resulting in reduced Co and Pb bioaccumulation. presented a new promising agrotechnical practice of reducing [21]. Co is not considered an essential element for humans in its inorganic form. Excessive consumption of Co has genotoxic, hepatotoxic, nephrotoxic, neurotoxic and immunotoxic effects on human and animal health [25, 9], combined consumption is associated with certain diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's and autism [12]. Maximum permissible levels of Co concentration in rice and other food products have not yet been established by the WHO or any other organization [24].

The permissible amount for cobalt is 1 mg/kg. During the experiment, it was observed that the root system of the Alanga variety was 1.14 times more than MPC during the first vegetation period, and during the second vegetation period, it increased from MPC in the

In the second year of the season, the content of the grain obtained from the Alanga variety was lower than that of the control variant, and was 0.48 mg/kg. Lead element ions were observed to bioaccumulate at the same rate regardless of the state of contamination in Alanga grain. 3- and 5-fold contamination with Pb and the same contamination with other elements also showed bioaccumulation of 1.20-1.23 and 1.61-1.80 mg/kg, and 2.39-2.46 and 3,39-2.46 from MPC. It was found to be 22-3.60 times more (Fig. 14).

No bioaccumulation of element ions was observed in the grain obtained from Lazer variety in the first season in all variants, in the case of 3 and 5 times pollution with a single element from MPC 0.77-0.98 mg/kg (1.54-1.97 times higher than MPC), complex with elements At 3- and 5-fold contamination, 1.29-1.41 mg/kg (2.57-2.81 times higher than MPC) was observed (Fig. 14).

following ways: in the control option, by 2.73 times → in the Co (3 MPC) option, 4.67 times the highest bioaccumulation was observed in the variant → Co (5 MPC) by 8.41 times → complex Co (3 and 5 MPC) by 2.57 and 6.93 times (Figure 15).

In the root system of the Lazer cultivar, it was observed that Co increased in the first season by 1.62 times in the control option, and by 2.30 and 3.75 times in the options polluted with the element ion by 3 and 5 times. 3- and 5-fold variants of complex contamination did not increase from MPC. During the second season of vegetation, on the contrary, a large amount of bioaccumulation of MPC by 1.70→4.04→6.63→4.45→5.75 times was observed in the roots of the cultivar Alanga (Fig. 15).

The bioaccumulation of cobalt in the root system was observed to be high in the roots of both cultivars, and it can be seen that it was higher in the root system of the Lazer variety in complex contamination. In the root system of the variety "Alanga" a high rate of Co 5 MPC is distinguished by bioaccumulation of 8.41 mg/kg. This situation leads to separation of toxicants by trapping them in the root system and low bioaccumulation in the consuming parts (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Bioaccumulation of cobalt ions in the root system, mg/kg

In conclusion, as mentioned above, the amount of cobalt retained by the root system in the root system leads to their bioaccumulation in small amounts in the above-ground parts. According to the analyzes of the stem and leaf system obtained from Alan and Lazer cultivars, less bioaccumulation was observed than MPC. A large amount of bioaccumulation of elements was observed in the grain part, but it is characterized by the ability of the root system to capture ions and reduce the movement of the element in the above-ground part of the plant.

Along with Cd and Ni uptake, shoot and root length decrease was observed, and metal treatment also caused a decrease in K, Ca, and Mg content in plants, especially in shoots, suggesting that Cd and Ni not only affect nutrient uptake, but also nutrient availability to different parts of the plant. also interferes with the spread of substances [26].

Cadmium is readily absorbed by the roots of growing seedlings and its localization is more concentrated in the roots than in the shoots [18]. In addition, silicon Silicon (Si) alleviates cadmium (Cd) toxicity and accumulation in a number of plant species, but the exact molecular mechanisms responsible for this effect are still poorly understood [17]. Nickel with an average of 2.38 ± 0.81 UCP shows the highest standard deviation of. The mean USPI for brass is in the following decreasing order: Cd (0.95 ± 0.45) > Ni (0.92 ± 0.64) > Pb (0.84 ± 0.41) > Cr (0.69 ± 0.25) > Zn (0.36 ± 0.068). Cadmium and nickel showed the highest and lowest BAF with an average of 0.302 and 0.0067

respectively [19]. While in the studies of Ezeofor et al average amount of metals in soil (mg/kg) Ni (0.57 ± 0.24), Pb (2.44 ± 0.17), Zn (3.35 ± 2.05), Cu (0.71 ± 0.33), Mn (37.72 ± 10.97), Fe ($13,856.6 \pm 31.43$), Cr (2.51 ± 0.98), Cd (0.51 ± 1.36) and Hg (0.02 ± 0.38); but metals found in rice grains (mg/kg): Ni (0.81 ± 0.72), Pb (0.94 ± 0.70), Zn (8.22 ± 2.97), Cu (0.59 ± 0.42), Mn (13.30 ± 4.56), Fe (13.28 ± 0.73), Cr (15.00 ± 10.00), Cd (0.36 ± 0.07) and Hg (0.002 ± 0.23) [10].

The data presented above show that the amount of certain toxicants present in the soil is high in plants. Because plant roots do not fully cover the soil cover and 1.95 kg of soil is needed for one plant. The root system of the rice plant is closely connected with the soil. Therefore, purification by plants through bioaccumulation of toxicant ions is included in biological purification methods.

The MPC for nickel is set at 1.0 mg/kg. During the first season, nickel element ions were only 1.15 mg/kg higher than the MPC, 1.15 times higher than the MPC of the replicates contaminated with 5 times the complex of elements. During the second season, a sharp bioaccumulation of nickel ion was observed, which was 3.52-7.54-11.26-3.31-6.53 mg/kg. This situation was also observed in the Lazer variety of rice, which accumulated only 2.79 mg/kg from the control variant in the first season, and bioaccumulation was observed from the control variant as follows: from MPC 1.95 → 4.11 → 5.20 → 4.02 → Up to 5.46 times higher accumulation was detected. The retention of nickel element ions in the roots of both varieties reduces the toxicity of plants for consumption (Fig. 16).

Figure 16. Bioaccumulation of nickel in the root system, mg/kg

The average amount of nickel in the stem and leaf system of rice varieties is less than that of MPCs in both seasons, and the bioaccumulation process of 0.894 mg/kg was carried out in the Laser variety of the control

variant, and 1.20 → It was observed that it was 3.63→1.91→2.15 times or mg/kg, and in the second season, the process of bioaccumulation of the toxicant in the plant was less than MPC (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Bioaccumulation of nickel ions in the stem, mg/kg

The selected control soil was an irrigated typical gray soil with a Ni content of 4.72 mg/kg, 1.18 times that of MPC. Nickel, like other elements, did not bioaccumulate directly to plants in the first year from artificially contaminated soil. In the grain composition of the Alanga cultivar, during the first season of the season, nickel ion was less than MPC, and during the second season, it was 0.37 mg/kg in the control variant, 1.12 and 1.04 mg/kg in the variants with 3 and 5 times contamination of the element, and 0 in the complex contamination variants. Bioaccumulation was observed

in the amount of 56-1.12 mg/kg. It was found that the amount of toxicants in the grain part of the Laser variety was less than that of MPC during both seasons (Fig. 18).

In conclusion, the bioaccumulation of elements in the process of absorption of toxicants by the selected varieties is characterized by high retention in plant parts. Because it was determined that nickel was accumulated in the roots of both varieties more than MPC, i.e. it was 1.95 to 11.26 times higher.

Figure 18. Bioaccumulation of nickel in grain, mg/kg

The MPC for cadmium in cereals is set at 0.5 mg/kg. Bioaccumulation of 0.06-0.35 mg/kg, a total of 0.41 mg/kg, was observed in the Alanga variety from the control variants. In the laser variety, the same amount of 0.61 mg/kg was determined in both seasons. This means that it is increased from MPC. The selected control soil had a cadmium content of 0.23 mg/kg (Figure 19).

High bioaccumulation was observed in the roots of Lazer variety at 3 times artificial contamination with cadmium element, 2.81 mg/kg, 5.62 times higher than MPC. No bioaccumulation was observed in the roots of

the cultivar Alanga during the first season of artificial contamination. In the second season, in the roots of Alanga variety, 0.78 mg/kg (1.56 times of MPC) of the variant with 5 times more Cd than MPC, and 0.94 mg/kg (1.88 times of MPC) in the Lazer variety. 0.67-0.80 mg/kg bioaccumulation was observed in the roots of the variety. Bioaccumulation of more than 0.02-0.30 mg/kg of MPC was observed in the roots of the Alangan variety (Fig. 19).

A large amount of cadmium bioaccumulation in the roots can prevent the production of edible crops, i.e., its transfer into the grain.

Figure 19. Bioaccumulation of cadmium ion in the root system, mg/kg

The MPC for the element cadmium is 0.1 mg/kg. In the stems of both cultivars selected for the laboratory experiment, Cd element ion bioaccumulated less than MPC. Control variants accumulated Cd ion in the amount of 0.06-0.03 mg/kg.

0.21-0.19 mg/kg in the stem of the Alanga variety in the variant with 3 and 5 times more contaminated than the MPC, 0.17-0.30 mg/kg in the Lazer variety, 0.20-0.16 mg/kg, in the variant with 5 times the MPC 11 and

0.08-0.16 mg/kg bioaccumulation was observed (Fig. 20).

A high bioaccumulation of the elements in the variants 3 times more polluted than MPC was observed in the second season at 0.48 mg/kg Alanga stem, it was found to be 4.8 times higher than MPCs. This situation was not observed in the MPCaining variants (Fig. 19). When the elements are 5 times more complex than MPC, the bioaccumulation of element ions in the stem of both varieties is less than MPC.

Figure 20. Bioaccumulation of cadmium element ion in stem part, mg/kg

According to the analysis, the cadmium element in the initial soil composition was found to be 0.23±0.001 mg/kg. In the options where the control was soil, the second season grain yield obtained from the Alanga variety increased by 1.2 times compared to MPC, and bioaccumulation up to 0.04-0.08 mg/kg was observed in the MPCaining cases.

In variants with a single element contaminated 3 times from MPC, the grain yield of the Alanga variety increased by 4.8 times the norm in the first season, and in other variants it was 1.3-1.5 times more than MPC. In the second season of the grain of the Laser variety, it

was less accumulated than MPC, that is, bioaccumulation of 0.03 mg/kg was observed. Bioaccumulation of 0.04-0.03 mg/kg was observed in the variant contaminated 5 times more than MPC by 1.5-1.3 times, and less than MPC by 0.04-0.03 mg/kg in the grain of Lazer variety (Fig. 20).

During both seasons, even in the complex state, in the grain of the Alanga variety from the variant soil with 3 times more Cd, it is 1.1-2.5 times more than MPC, and in the grain of the 5-fold variant, it is 1.3-2.8 times (Fig. 21).

Figure 21. Bioaccumulation of cadmium ion in grain, mg/kg

In conclusion, it was observed that the bioaccumulation of Cd element ion is less in the grain part of Lazer variety compared to Alanga variety, and it was determined that the planting of Lazer variety in areas contaminated with cadmium does not cause negative effects on human health.

Condition of soil contaminated with toxicants after a phytoremediation event

The composition of a typical irrigated gray soil selected for laboratory experiments was examined in a normal nitric acid, high pollution in the mobile forms of elemental ions belongs to the element nickel, and the soil has been continuously saturated with mineral fertilizers. The MPC for the mobile form of nickel was 4

mg/kg, and the soil content was found to be 9.72 mg/kg, 2.43 times higher than the MPC. Lead and copper elements in the soil are 10.27 and 5.26 mg/kg, 1.71 and 1.73 times higher than MPCs (Table 10).

After artificial contamination of the soil, Alanga and Lazer varieties of rice were planted twice during two growing seasons in 2021 and 2022. The bioaccumulation of elemental ions in plant organs was calculated in planted plants, and chemical analyzes of soil composition were carried out in repeated versions.

The mobile forms of chromium, cadmium and cobalt elements in the soil composition are less than MPC, and zinc element is around the level of MPC, approaching 0.98 times.

Table 10

Content of heavy metals in typical irrigated gray soil, mg/kg							
Item/ MPC	Cu/3	Zn/23	Cr/6	Co/5	Ni/4	Pb/6	Cd/0.5
mg/kg	5.26±0.09	22.65±0.32	2.74±0.05	2.53±0.01	9.72±0.02	11.32±0.32	0.32±0.21
amount of MPC	1.73	0.98	0.46	0.51	2.43	1.71	0.23

Bioremediation is a complex of soil and water treatment methods based on the use of biochemical capabilities of microorganisms (bacteria, fungi), algae and higher plants [39]. The MPCoval of toxic substances from the soil occurs in the event of phytoremediation.

Copper element was found to be 3.84 mg/kg after the first season and 2.92 mg/kg after the second season in the control variant. The scientific works of Kh.T. Riskieva and Kh.N.Karimov show that each toxic element included in the soil causes the agrochemical composition of the soil to become stressed in the first year.

In laboratory experiments, the total number of options was 20, and to compare the analyzes 1) Control, 2) Cu(3 MPC) + soil, 3) Cu (5 MPC) + soil, 4) Complex

Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil, 5) Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd +Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil variants were extracted and the MPCaining elemental variants were analyzed in a similar manner.

Due to the abundance of copper in the soils of the control option, bioaccumulation of 3.14 mg/kg in Alanga and 2.61 mg/kg in Lazer variety was observed in plants obtained from the control option. The highest bioaccumulation was observed in the Alanga variety over two years, and formed a decreasing series according to variants as follows: average in the Alanga variety 9.42→5.42→4.75→4.11 mg/kg, and in the Laser variety contaminated with one element 5 and variants 3 showed high bioaccumulation, i.e. 8.01→7.10 and 5.37→4.36 mg/kg (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Amount of residual copper ions in the soil, mg/kg

Due to the presence of copper ions (5.26±0.09 mg/kg) in the soil of the control option, bioaccumulation was observed in cultivar plants during two growing seasons. element residues are identified.

Due to the high amount of bioaccumulation of copper element in MPCs in the 3-fold and 5-fold contaminated options, the content of the soil of the variant with the Alanga variety was 7.46 mg/kg, in the soil of the Lazer variety 12.31 mg/kg, and in the 5-fold 10.22-14.83 mg/kg element residual amounts were determined (Table 11).

The introduction of toxicants into the complex soil will certainly affect the agrochemical condition of the soil, changing the amount of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. The element absorbed by plants is therefore close to one of the options in complex pollution with toxicants, and no phytoremediation phenomenon was observed. Because bioaccumulation of low elemental ions in plants was observed in complex pollution (Table 11).

Table 11

Amounts of residues after phytoremediation of copper element, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Lazer soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	3.84±0.33	2.92±0.69	3.95±1.46	2.13±0.84
Cu(3 MPC) + soil	8.59±1.81	7.72±1.45	10.87±2.12	9.04±0.97
Cu(5 MPC) + soil	14.78±1.42	13.57±0.31	14.38±0.81	18.07±0.70
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	8.33±0.32	7.46±0.80	11.13±1.14	12.31±1.31
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	12.39±2.80	10.22±0.37	15.52±0.99	14.83±1.52

In conclusion, the presence of toxicants in excess of MPCs and the artificial introduction of elements lead to the formation of complex elements, which cause an increase in their content in the soil during the next vegetation years. In addition, the amount of elements increases with the re-release of element ions absorbed by microorganisms.

The presence of zinc element in the control soil (22.65±0.32 mg/kg) was observed bioaccumulation of

19.20 mg/kg in Alanga variety plant and 24.78 mg/kg in Lazer variety plant for two years. and it was determined to be 8.10-13.52 mg/kg, respectively (Fig. 22).

The amount of element ions in the soils polluted 3-5 times higher than MPCs is 34.80-49.66 mg/kg in the Alanga variety, and 38.71-31.00 mg/kg in the Lazer variety plants, and 50.17-53 in the complex polluted variants, respectively. ,36 mg/kg, bioaccumulation was observed at 45.33-48.41 mg/kg (Fig. 23).

Figure 23. Amount of residual zinc from soil composition, mg/kg

The lowest amount of residual elements in the soil was observed in plants of the Lazer variety, it was found to be 13.82 mg/kg in the soil of the 3 times complex variant, and 23.96 mg/kg in the soils of the Alanga variety (Table 12).

Table 12

Amount of residual zinc toxicant in the soil, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Lazer soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	8.85±2.25	8.10±3.81	16.11±2.67	13.52±2.37
Ms(3 MPC) + soil	57.14±1.87	26.14±5.27	70.78±20.45	60.70±11.64
Ms(5 MPC) + soil	66.54±9.5	52.09±11.09	96.44±10.75	59.82±2.74
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	47.41±0.39	23.96±4.34	51.07±5.16	13.82±1.54
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	75.80±3.58	41.60±6.13	81.96±3.63	53.81±8.42

The MPC for the mobile form of chromium element in the soil is 6 mg/kg, and it is 2.74 ± 0.05 mg/kg in the control soil.

During two years, bioaccumulation of chromium element ion absorbed by plants was 1.94 mg/kg in Alanga variety and 2.13 mg/kg in Laser variety plants, and 2.08-1.95 mg/kg toxicant residues were detected in control soil.

Figure 24. Amount of chromium bioaccumulation by plants for two years, mg/kg

As a result of planting rice for two years, Chromium was bioaccumulated more in Lazer variety plants than in Alanga variety plants, and it was determined that it was $7.56 \rightarrow 9.88 \rightarrow 7.82 \rightarrow 9.43$ mg/kg in the soil composition (Table 13).

Table 13

Chromium content in soil, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Laser soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	2.36 ± 0.83	2.08 ± 0.33	2.24 ± 0.82	1.95 ± 0.02
Cr(3 MPC) + soil	16.90 ± 0.04	14.15 ± 9.12	9.55 ± 0.66	7.56 ± 1.22
Cr(5 MPC) + soil	22.89 ± 2.06	19.04 ± 8.43	11.44 ± 3.50	9.88 ± 1.15
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	15.93 ± 9.63	12.21 ± 0.65	10.35 ± 2.75	7.82 ± 2.53
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	26.00 ± 4.58	21.85 ± 4.89	13.47 ± 3.21	9.43 ± 1.89

It was found that residual Cr was 2.33-3.17 times higher than MPC in variants, and 2.04-3.64 times higher in complex variants when the variety was planted in Alanya with 3 and 5 times contamination (Table 13).

MPC for the mobile form of cobalt element in the soil composition was 5 mg/kg, and the control soil composition was found to be 2.53 ± 0.01 mg/kg. After phytoremediation of plants during two growing seasons in the control soil, the element content was 1.86 mg/kg in the variant planted with the Alan cultivar, and 1.89 mg/kg in the Laser cultivar (Table 14).

Table 14

Amount of residual cobalt in the soil, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Laser soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	2.13 ± 0.95	1.86 ± 0.38	2.13 ± 0.21	1.89 ± 0.08
Co(3 MPC) + soil	5.78 ± 2.01	4.39 ± 1.58	7.89 ± 0.06	7.796 ± 0.34
Co(5 MPC) + soil	8.28 ± 1.20	7.38 ± 0.22	11.98 ± 0.23	9.51 ± 2.18
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	11.60 ± 1.07	2.79 ± 0.16	7.21 ± 0.41	2.34 ± 0.081
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	4.51 ± 0.82	4.16 ± 2.75	10.20 ± 0.99	7.50 ± 0.76

4.39 and 7.38 mg/kg in the soil of variants planted with Alanga variety rice contaminated 3 and 5 times by the phytoremediation method carried out by the plant, 2.79-4.16 mg/kg in complex variants, 7.80-9.51-2.34-7.50 mg/kg Co was found (Table 14).

Figure 25. Amount of bioaccumulation of cobalt ions by rice during two growing seasons, mg/kg

The MPC of the mobile form in soil for element nickel was 4 mg/kg, which was 2.83 times the MPC of the control soil and accumulated at 9.72 mg/kg. After two seasons, a decrease of 1.95-4.3 mg/kg was observed in the soil of the control variant. It was determined that the soil content of the MPCs of nickel was reduced by 6.27 mg/kg in the variant soils planted with Alanga variety, and by 9.36 mg/kg in the soil with Lazer variety plants. 7.95-13.54 mg/kg MPCained in the soil of the option 5 times higher than MPC (Table 15).

Table 15

Amount of residual nickel toxicant in the soil, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Laser soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	6.80±0.96	1.95±0.13	5.08±0.50	4.30±0.37
Ni(3 MPC) + soil	15.10±1.18	6.27±1.16	11.61±0.77	9.36±3.83
Ni(5 MPC) + soil	17.53±1.12	7.95±2.49	15.71±2.25	13.54±1.82
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	15.29±1.14	5.83±0.59	10.24±0.55	4.61±0.12
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	18.46±0.72	8.99±0.19	15.78±1.77	11.21±0.97

Residual amounts of the elements were determined in the soil of the Alanga variant, 3 and 5 times more polluted than MPCs, 5.83-8.99 mg/kg, and 4.61-11.21 mg/kg in the soils planted with the Laser variety.

3.33-4.70 mg/kg in plants of Alanga variety, 1.74-2.46 mg/kg in Lazer variety, 2.16-3.50 mg/kg of complex contamination variants with 3 and 5 times MPCs for two years and 1.80-2.59 mg/kg bioaccumulation took place (Fig. 26).

Figure 26. Amount of bioaccumulation of nickel ions in plants during two growing seasons, mg/kg

MPC for the mobile form of elemental lead in the soil composition was determined to be 6 mg/kg, and it was found to be 10.27 ± 0.47 mg/kg in the control soil. Using phytoremediation, it was determined that Alanga plants MPCoved 2.02 mg/kg of toxicants from the control soil and 1.98 mg/kg with Lazer plants.

Bioaccumulation process of both varieties of lead in the range of 7.01-4.81 mg/kg took place from 5 times contaminated soils (Table 16).

Table 16

Residual amount of lead in the soil after two vegetations, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Laser soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	10.44 ± 1.57	4.75 ± 2.01	9.08 ± 1.11	7.75 ± 0.55
Pb(3 MPC) + soil	17.44 ± 1.10	14.99 ± 6.20	24.03 ± 1.41	17.99 ± 6.77
Pb(5 MPC) + soil	23.77 ± 0.22	19.87 ± 9.71	29.61 ± 3.93	18.64 ± 1.88
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	19.37 ± 0.25	12.18 ± 0.32	18.25 ± 1.39	13.79 ± 3.20
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	26.70 ± 2.78	14.08 ± 6.21	27.41 ± 3.13	19.89 ± 1.59

The MPC for the mobile form of cadmium in soil is 0.5 mg/kg, and a mean of 0.32 ± 0.001 mg/kg was found in selected irrigated typical gray soils. About 23-32% bioaccumulation of cadmium element by phytoremediation method was observed using rice plants from control soil options.

During the first vegetation, Alanga cultivar plants had a bioaccumulation of around 0.49-0.45 mg/kg, and Lazer cultivar plants had a bioaccumulation of 0.62-0.52 mg/kg in both variants polluted with cadmium element 5 times from MPCs. The amount of the residual element was found to be 1.55-1.76 mg/kg in Alanga variety variants and 0.76-1.74 mg/kg in the soils of the variant where Lazer variety plants were planted.

Table 17

Amount of residual cadmium in the soil at the end of the laboratory experiment, mg/kg

Options	The composition of the soil in the flame		Laser soil composition	
	2021	2022	2021	2022
Control soil	0.30 ± 0.23	0.25 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.09	0.22 ± 0.20
Cd(3 MPC) + soil	1.14 ± 0.12	0.86 ± 0.30	1.02 ± 0.28	0.23 ± 0.01
Cd(5 MPC) + soil	2.06 ± 0.01	1.55 ± 0.64	1.80 ± 0.10	0.76 ± 0.16
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (3 MPC) + soil	1.17 ± 0.14	0.98 ± 0.25	1.30 ± 0.28	0.25 ± 0.04
Complex Cu+Pb+Ni+Cd+Cr+Co+Zn (5 MPC) + soil	2.18 ± 0.09	1.76 ± 0.29	1.87 ± 0.27	1.74 ± 0.34

During the two growing seasons, bioaccumulation of 0.61-1.34 mg/kg of plants of the Flame and Lazer cultivars was carried out in variants contaminated with 3 times the MPC of the element, residual amounts of cadmium in the soil were 0.86-0.23 mg/kg (Table 17, Figure 27).

Figure 27. Bioaccumulation of cadmium ion in plants during two growing seasons, mg/kg

In conclusion, it can be explained by the fact that the process of bioaccumulation corresponds to the residual amounts of elements MPCaining in the soil, and in some cases, their sorption by microorganisms. Because the amount of residual toxicant differs from the amount of heavy metal absorbed by the plant.

References

1. Abdelgawad H, Mohammed AE, van Dijk JR, Beemster GTS, Alotaibi MO, Saleh AM. The impact of chromium toxicity on the yield and quality of rice grains produced under ambient and elevated levels of CO₂. *Front Plant Sci.* 2023 Mar 7;14:1019859. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1019859. PMID: 36959941; PMCID: PMC10027917.
2. Abdelgawad H, Mohammed AE, van Dijk JR, Beemster GTS, Alotaibi MO and Saleh AM (2023) The impact of chromium toxicity on the yield and quality of rice grains produced under ambient and elevated levels of CO₂. *Front. Plant Sci.* 14:1019859. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1019859.
3. Agnew UM, Slesinger TL. Zinc Toxicity. [Updated 2022 Dec 11]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK554548/>.
4. Appenzeller-Herzog C, Mathes T, Heeres MLS, Weiss KH, Houwen RHJ, Ewald H. Comparative effectiveness of common therapies for Wilson's disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis of controlled studies. *Liver Int.* 2019 Nov;39(11):2136-2152. [PubMed].
5. Balali-Mood, M.; Naseri, K.; Tahergorabi, Z.; Khazdair, MR; Sadeghi, M. Toxic Mechanisms of Five Heavy Metals: Mercury, Lead, Chromium, Cadmium, and Arsenic. *Front Pharmacol* 2021, 12, 643972, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.643972>
6. Basit F., Chen M., Ahmed T., Shahid M., Noman M., Liu J., et al.. (2021). Seed priming with brassinosteroids alleviates chromium stress in rice cultivars via improving ROS metabolism and antioxidant defense response at biochemical and molecular levels. *Antioxidants* 10, 1089. doi: 10.3390/antiox10071089 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar][Ref list]
7. Bhattacharyya P, Chakraborty A, Chakrabarti K, Tripathy S, Powell MA. Chromium uptake by rice and accumulation in soil amended with municipal solid waste compost Volume 60, Issue 10, September 2005, Pages 1481-1486.
8. Camarata MA, Ala A, Schilsky ML. Zinc Maintenance Therapy for Wilson's Disease: A Comparison Between Zinc Acetate and Alternative Zinc Preparations. *Hepatol Commun.* 2019 Aug;3(8):1151-1158. [PMC free article] [PubMed].
9. Carrijo DR, Akbar N., Reis AFB, Lee C., Gaudin ACM, Parikh SJ, Green PG, Linquist BA Impacts of variable soil drying in alternate wetting and drying rice systems on yields, grain arsenic concentration and soil moisture dynamics. *Field Crop. Res.* 2018;222:101–110. [Google Scholar][Ref list].
10. Ezeofor, Chidinma C., Ihedioha, Janefrances N., T. Ujam, Oguejiofo, Ekere, Nwachukwu R. and Nwuche, Charles O. "Human health risk assessment of potential toxic elements in paddy soil and rice (*Oryza sativa*) from Ugbawka fields, Enugu, Nigeria" *Open Chemistry*, vol. 17, no. 1, 2019, pp. 1050-1060. <https://doi.org/10.1515/chem-2019-0121>.
11. Giri, S., Singh, AK (2017). Human health risk assessment due to dietary intake of heavy metals through rice in the mining areas of Singhbhum copper belt, India. *Environ. Sci. pollution. Res.* 24, 14945–14956. doi: 10.1007/s11356-017-9039-9.
12. Green B., Griffiths E., Almond S. Neuropsychiatric symptoms following metal-on-metal implant failure with cobalt and chromium toxicity. *BMC Psychiatr.* 2017;17:1–5. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar][Ref list].
13. Hasan GMMA, Das AK, Sutter MA. Accumulation of Heavy Metals in Rice (*Oryza sativa*. L) Grains Cultivated in Three Major Industrial Areas of Bangladesh. *J Environ Public Health.* 2022 Mar 8;2022:1836597. doi: 10.1155/2022/1836597. PMID: 35299874; PMCID: PMC8923786.
14. Hasan, G., Das, AK & Satter, MA 2022. Accumulation of Heavy Metals in Rice (*Oryza sativa*. L) Grains Cultivated in Three Major Industrial Areas of Bangladesh. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2022.
15. Honghong Li, Zhou Li, Shengcong Xie, Yongxin Huang, Miaofen Chen, Tuanhui Xie, Guo Wang. Accumulation and distribution of zinc in rice plants (*Oryza sativa* L.) growing in zinc contaminated paddy soils with biochar. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 2022, 10 (1), 106811. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106811>.
16. Jaishankar M, Tseten T, Anbalagan N, Mathew BB, Beeregowda KN. Toxicity, mechanism and health effects of some heavy metals. *Interdiscip Toxicol.* 2014 Jun;7(2):60-72. doi: 10.2478/intox-2014-0009. Epub 2014 Nov 15. PMID: 26109881; PMCID: PMC4427717.
17. Ji Feng Shao and others, Silicon reduces cadmium accumulation by suppressing expression of transporter genes involved in cadmium uptake and translocation in rice, *Journal of Experimental Botany*, Volume 68, Issue 20, 28 November 2017, Pages 5641–5651, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erx364>.
18. Kavita Shah, RS Dubey. A18 kDa cadmium inducible protein complex: its isolation and characterization from rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) seedlings, *Journal of Plant Physiology*, Volume 152, Issues 4–5, 1998, Pages 448-454, ISSN 0176-1617, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0176-1617\(98\)80262-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0176-1617(98)80262-9). (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0176161798802629>).
19. Masoumeh Fouladi, Maryam Mohammadi Rouzbahani, Sina Attar Roshan & Sima Sabz Ali-pour(2021) Health risk assessment of potentially toxic elements in common cultivated rice (*Oryza sativa*) emphasis on environmental pollution, *Toxin Reviews*, 40:4, 1019-1034, DOI:10.1080/15569543.2020.1818106.

20. Mido, Y.; Satake, M. Chemicals in the environment. In *Toxic Metals*; Sethi, MS, Iqbal, SA, Eds.; Discovery Publishing House: New Delhi, India, 2003; pp. 45–68
21. Mlangeni AT, Raab A, Feldmann J. Alleviating cobalt and lead toxicity in rice using zero valent iron (Fe⁰) amendments. *Helion*. 2022 Nov 26;8(11):e11928. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11928. PMID: 36468122; PMCID: PMC9713343.
22. Panich-pat T, Srinives P. Partitioning of lead accumulation in rice plants. *Thai Journal of Agricultural Science* 2009; 42(1): 35-40.
23. Praphaphan Krajanglikit, Jaraspong Nakkao, Jintanart Wongchawalit and Thanawan Panich-Pat. Lead Accumulation and Isolation of Associated Rhizobacteria in Rice Grown in Lead Contaminated Soil. pages 79 – 88. | DOI 10.14456/ea.2018.39
24. Rahman MA, Mahmudur M., Reichman SM, Lim RP, Naidu R. Heavy metals in Australian grown and imported rice and vegetables on sale in Australia: health hazard, Ecotoxicol. *Environ. Saf.* 2014;100:53–60. [PubMed] [Google Scholar][Ref list].
25. Reinholds I., Bartkevics V., Silvis ICJ, Van Ruth SM, Esslinger S. Analytical techniques combined with chemometrics for authentication and determination of contaminants in condiments: a review. *J. Food Compos. Anal.* 2015;44:56–72. [Google Scholar][Ref list],
26. Rubio, MI, Escrig, I., Martínez-Cortina, C. et al. Cadmium and nickel accumulation in rice plants. Effects on mineral nutrition and possible interactions of abscisic and gibberellic acids. *Plant Growth Regul* 14, 151–157 (1994).<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00025217>.
27. Sharma A., Kapoor D., Wang J., Shahzad B., Kumar V., Bali AS, et al.. (2020). Chromium bioaccumulation and its impacts on plants: An overview. *Plants* 9. doi: 10.3390/plants9010100 [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar][Ref list]
28. Singh, J.; Upadhyay, SK; Pathak, RK; Gupta, V. Accumulation of heavy metals in soil and paddy crop (*Oryza sativa*), irrigated with water of Ramgarh Lake, Gorakhpur, UP, India. *Toxicol. Environ. Chem.* 2011, 93, 462–473. [CrossRef]
29. Terrin G, Berni Canani R, Di Chiara M, Pietravalle A, Aleandri V, Conte F, De Curtis M. Zinc in Early Life: A Key Element in the Fetus and Preterm Neonate. *Nutrients*. 2015 Dec 11;7(12):10427-46. [PMC free article] [PubMed].
30. Umair Ashraf, U. Ashraf, Mian Habib-ur-Rahman Mahmood, M. Habib-ur-Rahman Mahmood, Saddam Hussain, S. Hussain, Farhat Abbas, F. Abbas, Shakeel Ahmad Anjum, S. Ahmad Anjum, & Xiangru Tang , H. Tang. (0000). Lead (Pb) distribution and accumulation in different plant parts and its associations with grain Pb contents in fragrant rice. *Chemosphere*, 248, 126003. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.126003
31. Wakeel, A., Hu, M., Gan, Y. (2020). Chromium-induced reactive oxygen species accumulation by altering the enzymatic antioxidant system and associated cytotoxic, genotoxic, ultrastructural, and photosynthetic changes in plants. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 21. doi: 10.3390/ijms21030728.
32. Witkowska D, Słowik J, Chilicka K. Heavy Metals and Human Health: Possible Exposure Pathways and the Competition for Protein Binding Sites. *Molecules*. 2021 Oct 7;26(19):6060. doi: 10.3390/molecules26196060. PMID: 34641604; PMCID: PMC8511997.
33. Hu, Jiakuan, Lian-xin Yang, Ziqiang Wang, Gui-chun Dong, Jian-ye Huang and Yulong Wang. "Toxicity of copper on rice growth and accumulation of copper in rice grain in copper contaminated soil." *Chemosphere* 62 4 (2006): 602–7.
34. Yu-Ping Yan, Jun-Yu He, Cheng Zhu, Chang Cheng, Xue-Bo Pan and Zhong-Yang Sun (2006). Accumulation of copper in brown rice and effect of copper on rice growth and grain yield in different rice cultivars. *Chemosphere* 65(10):1690-1696. DOI: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2006.05.022.
35. Zakaria Z, Zulkafflee NS, Mohd Redzuan NA, Selamat J, Ismail MR, Praveena SM, Tóth G, Abdul Razis AF. Understanding Potential Heavy Metal Contamination, Absorption, Translocation and Accumulation in Rice and Human Health Risks. *Plants*. 2021; 10(6):1070.<https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10061070>
36. Volkova Viktoriya Andreevna, Voronkova Natalya Artyomovna Zinc and the "soil-plant" system in the long-term application of mineral fertilizers and the conditions of the southern forest steppe of Omsk region // *Vestnik Ulyanovskoy GSXA*. 2021. No. 2 (54). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsink-v-sisteme-pochva-rastenie-pri-dlitelnom-primenenii-mineralnyh-udobreniy-v-usloviyah-yuzhnoy-lesostepi-omskoy-oblasti> (data obrashcheniya: 07.08 .2023).
37. Metodicheskie ukazaniya po opredeleniyu tyajelykh metallov v pochvakh selkhozugodiy i produktsii rastenievodstva / Izd. 2-e. Ministerstvo selskogo hozyaystva RF. M.: TsIANO, 1992. - 61 p.
38. Sheudjen A.Kh.. Agrochemistry in the field of agriculture // *Plodorodie*, no. 5 (92), 2016, pp. 22-27. (data processing: 07.08.2023).
39. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>